

Figure 1: Compiler Transformation of GHZ Parity Circuits on IQM Garnet

5-qubit GHZ — Submitted (logical)

5-qubit GHZ — Compiled (IQM Garnet native)

7-qubit GHZ — Submitted (logical)

7-qubit GHZ — Compiled (IQM Garnet native)

9-qubit GHZ — Submitted (logical)

9-qubit GHZ — Compiled (IQM Garnet native)

Legend: Hadamard (H) (green square), CNOT (blue square), RZ(ϕ) phase (orange square), PRX (native) (pink square), CZ (native) (purple square), Measurement (grey square)